

Studies on Ureas. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *N'*-Aryl-*N*³-2-*p*-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylaclylureas

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UREA derivatives¹ and oxadiazole² derivatives are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are anticonvulsants³ and are used in epilepsy. The present investigation was taken up with a view to synthesise more active urea drugs of type 1.

Cyanoacetic ester was reacted with hydrazine hydrate⁴ to get cyanoacetylhydrazide which was condensed with *p*-chlorobenzoic acid in presence of POCl₃ to get the corresponding 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives and the latter hydrolysed, and the corresponding acid chlorides were then condensed with substituted-phenylureas. The compounds synthesised were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, Pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian FT-80A spectrophotometer, using tetramethylsilane as the internal reference and mass spectra on a Varian MAT-CH₆-DF spectrometer.

2-*p*-Chlorophenyl-5-cyanomethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole :
A mixture of cyanoacetylhydrazide (0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorobenzoic acid (0.01 mol) and POCl₃ (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (1.54 g,

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF ARYL-*N*³-*N*²-2-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-5-YLACLYLUREAS

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% : Found/ (Calcd)	Zone of inhibition (mm)*					
						<i>S.a</i>	<i>S.ci</i>	<i>E.c</i>	<i>M.s</i>	<i>S.ce</i>	<i>A.n</i>
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	217	75	15.68 (15.73)	22	17	14	20	10	16
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	168	69	15.09 (15.14)	23	16	14	16	17	30
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	227	73	15.06 (15.14)	22	16	12	16	12	16
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	216	94	15.03 (15.14)	10	17	12	14	20	15
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	222	84	14.41 (14.51)	14	18	16	20	15	12
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	191	80	14.41 (14.51)	22	17	10	15	17	20
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	237	89	14.43 (14.51)	22	14	10	10	16	14
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	213	76	14.21 (14.36)	16	11	10	10	17	17
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	215	79	14.18 (14.36)	16	20	19	19	16	16
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂	192	82	14.27 (14.36)	15	17	18	13	19	12
11.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₄ Cl ₂	208	85	16.80 (16.91)	18	14	10	10	19	10
12.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	199	96	16.79 (16.91)	18	18	15	15	14	14
13.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	211	80	16.77 (16.91)	21	17	14	10	10	16
14.	<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	181	70	16.82 (16.99)	22	15	10	25	10	15
15.	<i>m</i> -Acetylphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	218	63	16.75 (16.99)	13	14	29	18	10	10
16.	<i>p</i> -Carbomethoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	191	69	12.73 (12.91)	15	12	27	26	18	22
17.	<i>α</i> -Naphthyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	245	58	12.98 (13.79)	10	12	19	16	13	18
18.	Benzyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	221	60	15.08 (14.15)	12	12	25	19	13	15
19.	2-Ethoxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	200	62	13.83 (14.00)	12	12	17	10	12	15

**S.a* = *S. aureus*, *S.ci* = *S. citrus*, *E.c* = *E. coli*, *M.c* = *M. serratia*, *S.ce* = *S. cerevisiae*, *A.n* = *A. niger*.

70%), m.p. 165° (Found: C, 54.33; H, 2.53; N, 18.89. $C_{10}H_6ON_3Cl$ requires: C, 54.79; H, 2.74; N, 19.18%).

2-p-Chlorophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole⁵: A mixture of 2-p-chlorophenyl-5-cyanomethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5 g) 10%, NaOH solution (80 ml) and alcohol (15 ml) was boiled under reflux for 1 h and then boiled for a few minutes in the open flask. It was then cooled and concentrated HCl added until the precipitation of the acid was complete, (4.5 g, 83%), m.p. 200° (Found: C, 50.33; H, 2.85; N, 11.63. $C_{10}H_7O_3N_3Cl$ requires: C, 50.42; H, 2.94; N, 11.76%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3100–2500br (OH), 1690 (C=O), 1550 (O=C–O), 1590 (C=N) and 1090 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

N'-Phenyl-N³-2-p-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylacylurea⁶: A mixture of 2-p-chlorophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.05 mol), dioxane (20 ml) and thionylchloride (5 ml) was heated under reflux at 70–80° for 6 h. The excess thionylchloride was then removed by distillation and the product was refluxed with phenylurea (0.01 mol) in dioxane (15 ml) for further 6 h. The contents were poured in ice-water and the excess phenylurea and acid was removed by treatment with boiling water and sodium hydroxide respectively, (0.9 g, 75%) (Found: C, 57.08; H, 3.21; N, 15.68. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N_4Cl$ requires: C, 57.3; H, 3.65; N, 15.73%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1680 (CONHCO), 1620 (C=N), 1540 (N–H def. + C–N str.), 1090 (C–O–C) and 680 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ (TMS; DMSO- d_6) 6.84–8.07 (9 H, m, ArH), 3.25 (H, s, OCH₂) and 8.88 (2H, s, NHCONH); m/z 52, 65, 80, 92, 95, 109, 123, (base peak) 134, (McLafferty rearrangement) 139 and 272.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening was carried out using cup-plate⁷ method against gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Marcansera serratia* and fungi like *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 50 μg . All the compounds showed moderate antimicrobial activity; however, compound bearing R=*o*-tolyl showed highest activity against *S. aureus* (23 mm). It was observed that fungi *A. niger* and *S. cerevisiae* were moderately sensitive to the compounds under investigation.

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Synthesis of 2-Hydroxy-4,6-diphenylpyrimidines and their Antimicrobial Activity†

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PYRIMIDINE derivatives are known to possess various biological activities¹. This initiated us to synthesise the title compounds and evaluate their possible antimicrobial activity.

Literature survey reveals that the synthesis of title compounds have not been undertaken. The 2-hydroxy-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidines were obtained by the cycloaddition² of an appropriate 2'-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (3) with urea in presence of ethylene glycol as solvent. Use of dimethylformamide in place of glycol gave poor yields.

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